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**“ZAMONAVIY TA’LIM TIZIMINI
RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNGA QARATILGAN
KREATIV G’OYALAR,
TAKLIFLAR VA YECHIMLAR”**

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STRUCTURE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR DERIVATIVES IN FRENCH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. *This article discusses the communicative-pragmatic aspects of phraseological units are studied in linguistics, and they are considered as a certain tool in creating the socio-psychological aspects of the language.*

Key words: *phraseological units, phraseological derivation, the communicative-pragmatic aspects, linguoculturology, a pragmatic effect, semantics contains, a complex relationship.*

СТРУКТУРА ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ И ИХ ПРОИЗВОДНЫХ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются коммуникативно-прагматические аспекты фразеологизмов, изучаемых в лингвистике, и они рассматриваются как определенный инструмент создания социально-психологических аспектов языка.*

Ключевые слова: *фразеологизмы, фразеобразования, коммуникативно-прагматический аспекты, лингвокультурология, прагматический эффект, семантика содержит, сложная связь.*

The changing nature of the language is a factor in the enrichment of the lexical layer, the creation of new words, and the discovery of new meanings. Derivative studies show that many language elements are borrowed from other languages, or a word is sometimes added to a root to form a new word, over time. Undergoes a semantic change and acquires new meanings. At the same time, such changes are also observed in contexts related to the communicative-emotional state. But studies show that mainly derivational changes are formed within the word, sometimes there is a change from a compound to a sentence. In this part, we will consider affix changes in words that are part of phraseological units.

At present, the communicative-pragmatic aspects of phraseological units are studied in linguistics, and they are considered as a certain tool in creating the socio-psychological aspects of the language. At the same time, the science of linguistics is looking for new approaches and solutions in this area, based on the accumulated experience. In modern fields, these problems are a priority and create certain research paradigms. By the end of the

20th century, these requirements have led to the formation of a communicative-pragmatic direction in linguistics, which today has become a priority stage of research. Because research in this direction can be compared or enriched with information from the fields of social philosophy, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, linguoculturology and cognitive linguistics.

In connection with the increase in research within the framework of the concept of "Language, Man and the World", scientists working in the field of phraseology also focus on determining the communicative originality and pragmatic features of phraseological units. Based on the communicative-pragmatic paradigm, language is interpreted as a social phenomenon and serves as a means of establishing communication and achieving certain goals in various situations of communication. In our work, the main task is to identify phraseological units and their derivatives, to study their communicative and pragmatic analysis.

—Phraseological unit is a verbal (verbal) product of a secondary reflection of the linguistic picture of the world. This feature increases the communicative and pragmatic potential of phraseological units, - D. Dobrovolsky described the peculiarity of phraseological units [1].

At the same time, phraseological units create a pragmatic effect necessary for the speaker to perceive the emotional state of the world and implement the communicative process. It should also be noted that the phraseological fund of the language is the source of words and concepts, culture and national spirit. According to scientists, words and expressions representing national identity exist on the basis of proverbs, idioms and aphorisms containing phraseological units. The emergence of phraseological units and their derivatives is based on extralinguistic factors: the history of the people, cultural traditions, a variety of lifestyles. Changes in the system of society, economic and technical revolutions also affect phraseological units when the language changes. For this reason A.Artemyeva called phraseologisms "a linguistic and cultural reflection of society." Phraseological units are also found in the works of other linguists. The national originality of phraseological units is reflected in their structure and expression. As we mentioned above, the basis of anthropocentric research in the creation of the linguistic picture of the world is also formed by phraseological units and idioms, and when analyzing these works, it is important to recognize the work of V. Telia. Language is inextricably linked with the personal characteristics of a person, and if it is deprived of this connection, then it will be difficult to call it a language. According to V. Telia, a phraseological unit is a kind of sign, and its semantics contains an emotional (emotional) attitude and expression of its communicative-pragmatic activity. There is a complex relationship between this sign and the person using it. In it, the main task is performed by a person who purposefully creates language units and penetrates into all spheres of human activity [2]. A communicative intent is a complex interweaving of the speaker's intentions and his personal meanings. When indicative and pragmatic attitudes are combined in it, the choice falls on the phraseological nomination. And the choice of language itself, as noted by V.N. Telia can be interpreted as a —speech act that characterizes the one who performs this act. If the speaker takes on the role of a

judge, then his personal view of the world, his position as a subject of speech, is made explicit when he chooses linguistic means containing connotations (Telia, 143-p) .

The communicative and pragmatic features of phraseological units and their derivatives in different languages should also be noted. In communicative and pragmatic features, it is revealed in certain situations of colloquial speech. For example, In the expression "être tiré à quatre clous" or —être tiré à quatre épingles|| (dressed to the nines) , we cannot replace one of its elements, because the expression would lose all its meaning [4], we cannot change one of its elements, because the expression would lose all its meaning. We can't say we're fired up. In idioms, all elements are basic. From this stems fixedness, the most characteristic property of these units (even if it manifests itself to varying degrees). This freezing results in the deviation from the grammatical or lexical norm, and the unity of form and meaning: characteristics that include idiomacy, which is related to the image that comes to mind as soon as we hear expression. In Uzbek, the expression "qo'li kalta bo'lmoq, qo'li yupqa bo'lmoq" is translated as —As long as one's arm". In this area of research, if we talk, in this case, about the works of Uzbek scientists, we can note the studies of Sh. Rakhmatullaev, A. Mamatov, M. Umarchodjaev. In their study, a phraseological unit means a linguistic phenomenon that exists in Uzbek and other languages in a ready-made and integral form [5].

In conclusion, noting that the main research to date is carried out in the field of anthropocentric linguistics, i.e. in relation to the problem of the human factor in language, we seek to study the reflection of its nature. In this concept, language definitions are specific means of communication in which phraseological units have a certain communicative and pragmatic meaning. In this regard, phraseological units have the ability to express the speaker's value attitude to the known world, his emotional state, to create a pragmatic effect necessary for the implementation of the communicative plan. It is generally recognized that the phraseological fund of a language is a national cultural carrier and source.

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